

Hybrid Tabu K Means Clustering for Data Leak Identification

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ABSTRACT

Today, there has been an explosion of Online Social Networking (OSN) that has resulted in damages to various organizations owing to data leakage by employees. The social networking behavior of employees, whether intentional or accidental, has given an opportunity for some persistent threats from attackers that realise techniques of social engineering aside from zero-day exploits that are undetectable. Clustering is normally achieved by means of finding any similarity among data for predefined attributes. Similar data are grouped into clusters. In this work, modified methodology of K-Means clustering employed to identify the groups based on common traits. In this work, the Genetic Algorithm (GA) with K-Means, Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) with K-Means, hybrid GA-Tabu Search (TS) with K-Means and hybrid PSO-TS with K-Means methods are proposed. The proposed hybrid algorithms are used to find better performance for data leakage identification in the social network. The experimental results have demonstrated that the proposed technique performs better in comparison to other methods.

Keywords: *Social Network, Data Leakage Prevention (DLP), K-Means Clustering, Tabu Search (TS), Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO).*

1 INTRODUCTION

In the modern lives of humans, Online Social Networks (OSNs) are becoming a very important element to be connected with one another. Around 82% of the online population make use of at least a single OSN like LinkedIn, Twitter, Google, or Facebook to facilitate relationship building, sharing experiences, and providing other types of services. By means of the OSNs, plenty of personal data can be published online and then retrieved by users around the world. Studies conducted earlier has shown the possibility to gather any hidden personal data from information that has been shared publicly. Also, the quality and availability of such

public data can result in a leakage of privacy owing to the reasons mentioned below: 1) mechanisms of privacy control that is the standard feature of the OSNs that continue to evolve. 2) the actual percentage of users that elect to avoid sharing information publicly has also been increasing [1]. So, privacy leakage can be avoided with a comprehensive policy of privacy control in place. But, this can prove to be a challenge owing to the findings below:

The computer security can be expressed as “the protection afforded to automated information systems to attain certain applicable objectives in terms of the preservation of integrity, confidentiality, and availability of the system resources (which includes information, data, telecommunication, software, hardware, and firmware). Data leakage has been stated as an unintentional and accidental distribution of sensitive or confidential data to a third party that is not permitted. Some common examples of such confidential data are Intellectual Property (IP), credit card information, patient data, and financial data from industry or business [2].

Generally, confidential data should be shared among various stakeholders such as human resources that work from outside the entire site (such as laptops), clients, or business colleagues. Therefore, it is important to share data to increase the chances of sensitive information that may later be found in an unauthorized location. The reason for such breach of data either a deliberate will or an unintentional mistake by a resource person either within or outside the site. Confidential data disclosure can result in serious damage to the organization. Data Leakage Prevention (DLP) solution can be called a new technical methodology to protect sensitive data from being obtained by wrong users from inside or outside the organization. This means certain specific data can be viewed only by authorized groups or individuals. “DLP solutions can detect and prevent any unauthorized attempt at copying or forwarding sensitive data either intentionally or unintentionally without any authorization by the party entitled to such sensitive information”. This means the DLP technique has been used for hiding all confidential data from being accessed by any unauthorized users. Also, the DLP can be a product or a solution designed for detecting the breach of data preventing data monitoring when in use, or while in usage or at storage of data. The DLP solutions address such data leaks found in three stages with a set of technologies [3]:

- **Data-at-Rest (DAR):** This is the data residing in the file system or storage. For example, this can refer to the financial data of the company stored.
- **Data-in-Use (DIU):** Data found at the endpoints like MP3 players, external or USB devices, and laptops which include all data used by the user.
- **Data-in-Motion (DIM):** All data that has been moving through (or that has been sent through) the entire network to the world outside through the Internet. This is applicable to all transmitted data both wire and wireless.

Data Leakage Detection (DLD) and the DLP have been facing various issues in the detection and prevention of data leakage. Identified are seven major challenges from earlier work that have been listed below [4].

- The first was data transactions that could happen in various channels in different ways. In case the data had been transmitted through the desired applications, it can either be detected or protected. However, if this data channel is found to be the one that is other than a specific application such as a USB or an email, it can be a very challenging task.
- The next challenge can be the modification of data in which data gets modified and this can result in a partial leakage to users. At times, there are different approaches to identify the entire pattern of sensitive content. So, it can fail to detect full or partial data leakage either without modification.
- The next challenge was to determine and provide suitable access rights to specific users in accordance with their levels of security that can be more complicated. There may be improper policies and guidelines that can affect the accuracy of the DLP. For this, access controls have to be configured.
- The next challenge can be the process of encryption and steganography to protect data from any unauthorized users. However, it may be a challenge to analyze such data content if the techniques of encryption are strong.
- The use of the concepts of watermarking can preserve the ownership and can also help in avoiding any data leakage. However, watermarking contents cannot be relied upon for such data. Furthermore, watermarked contents can be recovered easily. This results in several other challenges.
- Both integration and scalability for a vast domain can be a major challenge that normally results in scalability issues. If the size of the network is large, access specification, monitoring, and policy matching get difficult.
- Finally, detecting data leakage from the log will require a supervised learning process. This can create uncertainties and other issues. Such challenges have been observed from the literature. On the basis of such challenges, several works of research have been made as shown below.

Cluster analysis has been a primary method of data analysis in research. Clustering refers to the grouping a certain set of abstract or instances into classes that consist of similar objects and dissimilar to the other objects found in the other cluster [5]. The K-means, on the other hand, is easy to implement and is quite effective in most situations. But its performance is dependent on the centroids and their initial states that help in converging to the local optima as opposed to the global optima. It also attempts to reduce any intra-cluster variance and warrant that the result also has a global minimum variation. In the last 20 years or so,

there have been several heuristic methods proposed for overcoming such problems. For example, the TS algorithm and Simulated Annealing (SA) were applied to clustering. The GA-based approach was tested on various real datasets for performance evaluation [6].

The approaches of clustering are based on neural gas algorithms and there is a method used for cluster analysis that has been obtained from the Artificial Bee Colony (ABC) and the Ant Colony Optimisation (ACO). Furthermore, the Honey Bee Mating Optimisation (HBMO) algorithm was also applied for performing data clustering. Another type of data clustering that employs the big bang–big crunch algorithm was also introduced. An application of the PSO algorithm to the clustering problems had also been proposed. Yet another drawback that has been recognized with regard to the K-means method has the actual number of clusters that are required in the form of an input to the algorithm. There are certain approaches that can solve this problem. For the purpose of this work, the hybrid GA-TABU, PSO-TABU K-Means, and the K-Means processes are employed in the social network DLP. The rest of the investigation has been organized thus. Section 2 has explained the different methods employed. The results and conclusion have been discussed in Sections 3 and 4 respectively.

2 METHODOLOGY

In this section, the K-Means, GA K-Means, PSO K-Means, TS, GA-Tabu K-Means, and PSO-Tabu K-Means methods are discussed.

2.1 K-Means Algorithm

K-means refers to an iterative clustering procedure where the objects have been grouped amidst a certain set of clusters till such time desired result is achieved. This can be seen to be a squared error algorithm even though the convergence has to be defined on the basis of a squared error. There is a high degree of similarity among these elements and a higher degree of dissimilarity among them has been simultaneously achieved. K-means further takes an input parameter k , to partition a set consisting of n items into k clusters to ensure the resultant intra-cluster similarity is high with low intercluster similarity. Cluster similarity has been measured using the mean value of the objects found in the cluster and this is viewed as the center of gravity of the cluster [7].

K-means further groups items into a particular set of clusters that have been specified by the user. Firstly, it will make a random choice of k and this will initially indicate a certain cluster mean. For the leftover items, a new object is allotted to the cluster with high similarity. It now computes a new mean for the cluster and iterates the procedure until such time the function converges. The K-means algorithm can be sensitive to outliers. It is applicable only if the mean has been defined. There is a need to specify k in advance. Another limitation of this is the fact that it can terminate at a local optimum. For improving the actual performance of these underlying algorithms and to fix their weaknesses, a new and special technique in the form of GA or PSO can be applied.

3.2 GA-K-Means Algorithm

This refers to a search technique based on the concepts of genetics and natural selection. The concept of GA was formulated initially by Holland. It has its origin from the mechanism of evolution and natural selection by Darwin. It aims to solve optimization problems by using an objective function $f(x)$ where $x = [x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n]$ refers to the N dimensional vector with optimization parameters. It has also proven to be an effective, powerful, and efficient algorithm that forms problems of combinational optimization. There have been no differentiable or discontinuous object functions. The primary building blocks of such binary GAs are the genes and the chromosomes. The parameters of optimization have been encoded by means of the conventional binary to the binary code string. In order to develop and evolve better solutions, the selection was made with a parameter needed for discriminating the better solutions [8].

Taking the GA into consideration, this measure can function in an objective manner and prove to be a computer simulation model that is based on mathematics. It can also function subjectively in cases where the human can choose better methods. Essentially, these fitness measures should be able to find fitness that can be relative to its candidate solution and there the GA will make use of a direct rise or emergence for solutions that are better. Another essential aspect of the GA is known as population belief. Contrastingly, the GA is dependent on the candidate solutions. The size of the population is always a parameter that is determined only by the user and this has proven to be a major element that can influence the performance of the GA and also its scalability. For example, a population that is small-sized can result in an immature convergence thus offering solutions that fall below the standard. However, a large-sized population can result in a wastage of time that can be effectively used for the process of computing. Once the encoding is complete and a fitness parameter is chosen, the GA is ready to identify the best solutions using the steps given below:

1) *Initialization*: this refers to the primary or the starting solutions for population candidates produced by the search space in a random manner.

2) *Evaluation*: When the new population is generated and the population is initialized, fitness value evaluation for the candidate solutions is conducted.

3) *Selection*: there are more copies of solutions that are allocated by the selection of high-level fitness. The concept of survival of the fittest will be imposed on the candidate solutions. The primary notion was to select solutions that are better than favor the remaining ones. Thus, there are different selection processes that have been suggested for accomplishing such notions.

4) *Recombination*: This refers to the combining of two or more solutions with better solutions (offspring). This can be achieved by different methods where the efficiency of performance is based on the mechanism of recombination.

5) *Mutation*: When there are two or more such parental chromosomes operating by means of recombining, it can result in the modification of either the mutation which can be a random or local way to a solution. There are several distinctive types of mutation that normally include a change to the individual feature(s). So, mutation engages in performing a random walk in this vicinity.

6) *Replacement*: Here, the offspring population that is generated by the selection, mutation, and recombination can replace its original parental population.

7) All steps from 2 to 6 are repeated until the termination condition is met.

This method proposes a new and optimized K-means clustering algorithm [9] that combines the GA and its effectiveness in order to identify the results that are available for the K-Means. Also, the solution will be enhanced by using the Optimized Cluster Distance (OCD) method and this involves data re-clustering along with new centers that attempt to enlarge between the cluster distances (BSS) and decrease in the cluster distances (WSS).

Figure 1 GA Optimized K-means Clustering Flow diagram

The flow diagram of these algorithms is shown in Figure 1. In order to start the GA by means of producing its initial population based on the k which is given in the form of a limitation for a certain number of clusters, an estimation is made on the robustness of its initiatory population on k. This is, in turn, implemented in the form of a constant for the actual number of clusters. At this time, the fitness for the initial population of Mean Square

Error (MSE) is calculated. The actual distance between the center of the clusters and the data points that are remaining will be predicted and called the MSE. The approach will then move to the next level in case the user requires it to get better fitness than the one from the previous generation. From all these concerned particulars, the GA can accomplish features such as crossover, mutation, and selection for creating a new population as in (1).

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - c)^2 \quad (1)$$

Where c is the center from generated population in (2).

$$Fitness = \frac{1}{MSE} \quad (2)$$

By means of executing the K-Means, it can output the best GA-based centroids. Such centroids will provide the best results in terms of clustering. It has been recommended that OCD a novel technique having other processes be used. The method is used for minimizing the cluster variable and the actual distance between the clusters. Finally, the algorithm will choose various pairs of clusters with smaller distances compared to the overall average of the new cluster distances. Currently, the algorithm reclusters them with the GA and the K-Means. Based on this view, this can also cluster a small data subset and the algorithm can identify partitions that are away from one another compared to the OCD [10].

3.3 PSO-K-Means Algorithm

The PSO had been first proposed in the year 1995 by Kennedy and Eberhart. The algorithm imitates the bird foraging process to guide the process of optimization using swarm intelligence based on the particles in the swarm [11]. Every particle i will be connected to two different vectors which are position vector $X_i = [x_{i,1}, x_{i,2}, \dots, x_{i,n}]$ and velocity vector $V_i = [v_{i,1}, v_{i,2}, \dots, v_{i,n}]$. The particles will search for newer solutions by adjusting their respective positions $x_{i,d}$. For every particle, the individual historical optimal position will be searched as the $pbest_i$, and its current global optimal position was found by the particle swarm, as $gbest$. If there are two other optimal positions identified, every will update the position and velocity and position for equations (3) and Equations (4), respectively.

$$v_{i,d}(t+1) = \omega \cdot v_{i,d}(t) + c_1 \cdot rand_1 \cdot (pbest_{i,d} - x_{i,d}(t)) + c_2 \cdot rand_2 \cdot (gbest_d - x_{i,d}(t)) \quad (3)$$

$$x_{i,d}(t+1) = x_{i,d}(t) + v_{i,d}(t+1) \quad (4)$$

Wherein, t will be the t -th iteration, d the d -th dimension for the particle, ω the inertia weight, c_1 and c_2 the acceleration constants, $rand_1$ and $rand_2$ denote the random numbers that are randomly distributed within the interval [0, 1].

There is proof that the PSO and its performance can be improved in case the inertia weight ω linearly reduced. This decreased inertia weight has been shown as in (5):

$$\omega = \omega_{\max} - (\omega_{\max} - \omega_{\min}) \cdot \frac{t}{t_{\max}} \quad (5)$$

Wherein, ω_{\max} and ω_{\min} denote the maximal and the minimal weights; t is the actual number of current iteration, and t_{\max} the number of its maximum iteration.

3.4 TABU Search (TS) Algorithm

The TS, has been proposed by Glover, refers to a meta-heuristic method used for solving the problem of combinatorial optimization. There has been widespread attention given to this recently. It has a flexible framework of control with plenty of success in solving problems that are NP-hard resulting in rapid growth in its areas of application. This will differ from the technique of local search sensing the TS permitting to a new solution making the objective function less effective and does not keep it trapped into the local optimal solutions. The TS makes use of short-term memory known as the TABU List (TL) for recording and guiding the search process. Also, the TL uses long-term memories with regard to solutions improving intensification and diversification of search [13].

The TS scheme is further outlined in the following manner: start with the initial (or current) solution x known as the configuration, evaluate its criterion function for the solution. After this, follow a set of candidate moves known as the neighborhood $N(x)$ for their current solution x . In case the best of such moves is not TABU, (that is not in the TL) or if it is the TABU, but manages to satisfy the criterion of aspiration, a pick and move is taken to be the new solution. Repeat the entire process for a particular number of iterations. The best solution obtained until now will be the solution for the TS. It has to be noted that the solution picked for a particular iteration can be put in the TL to ensure it is not reversed to the subsequent 1 iterations. This is known as the TABU. Here, the size of the TL is 1. If the length of the TL reaches the same size, the first solution can be freed from being the TABU, and a new solution will be added to the list. This process will continue and the TL will remain as short-term memory. By means of recording the history of such searches, the TS will be able to control the direction of all searches. The aspiration criterion can reflect the value of its criterion function and in case the TABU solution ends up in a value of the criterion function which is considered better until now, the aspiration criterion will be met and the TABU restriction will be relieved and the solution will be arrived at. If S_b refers to the best solution that has been obtained until now, the TL will refer to the TABU List.

3.5 Proposed GA-TABU K-Means Algorithm

When the GA is applied as the second step, and the TS mechanism is applied to it, the quality of the solution is enhanced. While implementing every chromosome generated by the GA, a solution can be that it may go through crossover along with mutation and after each

mutation is complete, the solution can come with a TABU list and from among them the best that has better fitness value will be chosen. The GA is perhaps one of the best methods in global optimization which is a combination of both the algorithms to solve the problem of class timetabling [14]. The steps in the GA-Tabu K-Means algorithm as below:

1. Create the initial population in a random manner.
2. For every chromosome in the current population do.
 - 2.1. Calculate the fitness value of the current chromosome.
 - 2.2. Apply the tournament selection to both the chosen chromosomes.
 - 2.3. Apply a two-point crossover.
 - 2.4. Apply the mutation and compute the fitness for this chromosome.
3. Now the best chromosome having the best fitness value can be found.
4. Now insert the best solution of the GA to the TABU List.
5. While stop condition has been met
6. Evaluate the best solution.
7. Until the population size is complete.
8. Finally, obtain an optimal solution.

The figure 2 shows the flowchart for hybrid GA-Tabu algorithm.

Figure 2 Flowchart for Hybrid GA-Tabu Algorithm

3.6 Proposed PSO-Tabu K-Means Algorithm

For the purpose of avoiding premature convergence of the PSO, there have been several articles that were proposed. Furthermore, the hybrid methods that make use of the TABU search were proposed for solving the problem of discrete optimization in job shop scheduling. The TS can be quite efficient as a metaheuristic and was proposed in the year 1986 by Glover. This can memorize all regions visited in the search space given in the TABU list. The aim is to avoid revisiting solutions thus avoiding local optimum. Such prohibition can be temporary as it is dependent on the length of the TABU (TABU tenure).

This framework uses double TABU lists in the PSO [15]:

- The first tabu list, called the *infeasible_list*, handles infeasible solutions. It further memorizes these infeasible solutions within the list of a fixed size. If there is a new particle position that has been determined according to equations (3) and (4), it also checks if its falls under the *infeasible_list*. Here, the position may not be updated and the precedent position can be recovered. The aim was to make use of the *infeasible_list* for avoiding any check on solution feasibility.

- The second TABU list was used in the process of diversification that has been detailed below.

The process of Diversification

In order to deal with any risk involved in losing the solutions of diversification, on completion of several iterations of the PSO, the TS process has been embedded to the PSO as the local optimizer to the best local solution (*pbest*).

The TS had been adapted for the purpose of global optimization but adapting Chelouah and Siarry, the Enhanced Continuous Tabu Search (ECTS), showed good results and so the process has been inspired by this work.

The *pbest*solutions of the PSO can be the input to the procedure. For every s , there is a list of neighborhoods that have been defined. For these neighborhoods, all new solutions will be looked into and the one that is the best will replace its current solution. Now the solution s has been saved within a second TABU list known as *best_list*. This process will be repeated using new solutions until such time a defined stop criterion has been met.

The neighborhoods in the solution s have been defined by the hyper-rectangles that were introduced. A hyper-rectangle of s having a radius r will be the space search with solutions s' and the distance between s and s' is less than r .

For generating these m neighborhoods for a solution s , m hyper-rectangles that are centered on the s are created. From every hyper-rectangle, there is a point that is chosen randomly. The best among m chosen points will substitute s .

The steps that are employed in the PSO-Tabu K-Means algorithm are:

Step 1: Initialize the problem with all parameters of the algorithm

Step 2: Initialize the PSO parameters by employing K-Means clustering

Step 3: Improvise other new particles by employing the TABU algorithm

Step 4: Update the PSO

Step 5: Check for the stopping criterion

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The proposed methods GA K-Means, PSO K-Means, GA-Tabu K-Means, and PSO-Tabu K-Means methods are evaluated using Enron dataset. 90000 emails were used for evaluation of the algorithms. The summary of results are tabulated in table 1. The True Positive Rate (TPR) for the known and unknown recipient and False Positive Rate (FPR) for the known and unknown recipient and TP) obtained and the same are shown in figures 3 to 5.

Table 1 Summary of Results

	GA K Means	PSO K Means	GA-Tabu K Means	PSO-Tabu K Means
TPR for Known recipient	0.857	0.8546	0.857	0.8693
TPR for Unknown recipient	0.4895	0.5398	0.6241	0.6329
FPR for Known recipient	0.5105	0.4602	0.3759	0.3671
FPR for Unknown recipient	0.143	0.1454	0.143	0.1307

Figure 3 True Positive Rate (TPR) for PSO-Tabu K-Means

From figure 3, it is seen that the PSO-Tabu K-Means has higher TPR for the known recipient by 1.42% for GA K-Means, by 1.7% for PSO K-Means and by 1.42% for GA-TabuK-Means, respectively. The PSO-Tabu K-Means has higher TPR for the unknown recipient by 25.55% for GA K-Means, by 15.87% for PSO K-Means and by 1.4% for GA-Tabu K-Means, respectively.

Figure 4 False Positive Rate (FPR) for PSO-Tabu K-Means

From figure 4, it is seen that the PSO-Tabu K-Means has higher FPR for the known recipient by 32.68% for GA K-Means, by 22.51% for PSO K-Means and by 2.37% for GA-Tabu K-Means, respectively. The PSO-Tabu K-Means has higher FPR for the unknown recipient by 8.98% for GA K-Means, by 10.64% for PSO K-Means and by 8.98% for GA-Tabu K-Means, respectively.

Figure 5 True Positive (TP) Obtained for GA-Tabu K-Means

From figure 5, it is seen that the GA-Tabu K-Means has a higher average TP by 5.49% for GA K-Means, by 2.67% for PSO K-Means and by 4.33% for PSO-Tabu K-Means, respectively.

5 CONCLUSION

A social network refers to a social graph representing the relationship shared by users, their organizations, and social activities. In this work, an important feature is to provide a centralized admin system to hold control of sensitive data with specific processes if there is an attempt made for a data leak. K-Means clustering refers to the task of grouping a new set of objects to find them similar to one another compared to the ones in the other groups. The TS can be a process of iterative improvement beginning from an initial solution for determining a better one. Both GA and TS can be used for this. As the GA has a better ability of handling complex search spaces, there is a higher probability of success. The TS is used for its memorized ability to stop searching in areas visited earlier. The PSO can be quite easy to implement with very few adjusting parameters. It also suffers from slow convergence in its refined search stage (or the weak local ability of search). For this, the convergence time and the PSO combined with the TS can be easily solved based on the old solutions with the principle of memory that helps in avoiding backtracking (cyclical). Results show that the PSO-Tabu K-Means has higher TPR for the known recipient by 1.42% for GA K-Means, by 1.7% for PSO K-Means and by 1.42% for GA-Tabu K-Means, respectively. The PSO-Tabu K-Means has higher TPR for the unknown recipient by 25.55% for GA K-Means, by 15.87% for PSO K-Means and by 1.4% for GA-Tabu K-Means, respectively.

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